

Studies on 2-*o*-Anisylimino-3-*o*-anisyl-4-thiazolidone, 3-*o*-Anisyl-2, 4-thiazolidone, 2-*o*-Phenetylimino-3-*o*-phenetyl-4-thiazolidone, 3-*o*-Phenetyl-2, 4-thiazolidone, and the Fungicidal Activity of the Acetoxymcuri Derivatives of the Thiazolidiones

P. N. Bhargava, Miss Kamalini Bhargava, and R. C. Kapoor

2-*o*-Anisylimino-3-*o*-anisyl-4-thiazolidone, 3-*o*-anisyl-2,4-thiazolidone, 2-*o*-phenetylimino-3-*o*-phenetyl-4-thiazolidone, and 3-*o*-phenetyl-2, 4-thiazolidone have been synthesised and their characteristic reactions studied. The fungicidal activity of the acetoxymcuri derivatives of these thiazolidiones has been tested.

In continuation of our earlier work on 3-*m*-tolyl-2,4-thiazolidone and 5-arylo-3-phenyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidones (Bhargava *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 475), it was considered worthwhile to prepare 2-*o*-anisylimino-3-*o*-anisyl-4-thiazolidone, 3-*o*-anisyl-2,4-thiazolidone, 2-*o*-phenetylimino-3-*o*-phenetyl-4-thiazolidone, and 3-*o*-phenetyl-2,4-thiazolidone and to test the fungicidal activity of the acetoxymcuri derivatives of the thiazolidiones, referred to above.

The two new thiazolidiones have been prepared by interaction of the respective *S*-di-*o*-anisylthiourea and *S*-di-*o*-phenethylthiourea with monochloroacetic acid in ethanol in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate. The reactive methylene group of 2-*o*-anisylimino-3-*o*-anisyl-4-thiazolidone has been condensed with five aromatic aldehydes, and that of 3-*o*-anisyl-2,4-thiazolidone with four aromatic aldehydes, yielding 5-arylidene derivatives.

Mercuration of 3-*o*-anisyl-2,4-thiazodione with mercuric acetate has yielded a mercuri derivative, presumably 3-acetoxymcuri-*o*-anisyl-2, 4-thiazolidone. The acetoxymcuri group is expected to enter the aryl nucleus. Again, the reactive methylene group of 2-*o*-phenetylimino-3-*o*-phenetyl-4-thiazolidone has been condensed with five aromatic aldehydes and two aryldiazonium chlorides, yielding respectively 5-arylidene and 5-arylo-substituted thiazolidiones. Similarly the active methylene group of 3-*o*-phenetyl-2,4-thiazolidone has also been condensed with four aromatic aldehydes and two aryldiazonium chlorides.

The attachment of the azo group to -CH₂- group in position 5 in α -position to the activating carbonyl group is justified by the arguments advanced by Meerwein *et al.* (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, **152**, 237) and is further supported by the observation that when the -CH₂- group in position 5 of the thiazolidone or thiazolidone nucleus is blocked by condensation with aromatic aldehydes, no azo dye is formed. The latter thiazolidone on mercuration has yielded 3-acetoxymcuri-*o*-phenetyl-2, 4-thiazolidone.

Further, 2-*o*-phenetylimino-3-*o*-phenetyl-4-thiazolidone and 3-*o*-phenetyl-2, 4-thiazolidone on oxidation with KMnO₄ in glacial acetic acid have yielded the corresponding sulphones, as confirmed by analytical data.

Finally, 3-acetoxymcuri-*o*-anisyl-2, 4-thiazolidone, when tested for its fungicidal activity against the fungus *Alternaria solani*, has been found to inhibit completely the germination up to 66 p.p.m. Similarly, 3-acetoxymcuri-*o*-phenetyl-2, 4-thiazolidone, when tested against the fungus *Fusarium navile*, has been found to check germination of the spores up to a concentration of 26.58 p.p.m.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-o-Anisylimino-3-o-anisyl-4-thiazolidone was prepared according to the method of Klare *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2137) under conditions laid down by Bhargava and Kaul (this *Journal*, 1955, 38, 49) in a colorless crystalline form, m.p. 196.5°, maximum yield 81% under the optimum period of heating for 13.5 hours. (Found: S, 9.60. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 9.64%).

2-o-Phenetylimino-3-o-phenetyl-4-thiazolidone was obtained similarly, as above, in a dull yellow form, m.p. 118°; maximum yield 81.69% under optimum period of heating of 3 hours. (Found: S, 9.18. $C_{19}H_{20}O_3N_2S$ requires S, 8.78%).

3-o-Anisyl-2, 4-thiazolidone was prepared according to Klare *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) as white needles, m.p. 113.5°; maximum yield 50% under optimum period of heating of 11 hours. (Found: S, 14.29. $C_{10}H_9O_3NS$ requires S, 14.35%).

3-o-Phenetyl-2, 4-thiazolidone was obtained similarly in a yellow crystalline form, m.p. 84°; maximum yield 30.8% after a heating period of 4.5 hours. (Found: S, 13.35. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3NS$ requires S, 13.5%).

2-o-Anisylimino-3-o-anisyl-5-benzylidene-4-thiazolidone.—A mixture of thiazolidone (0.4 g.), benzaldehyde (0.2 c.c.), and pyridine (150 c.c.) were refluxed in an oil bath at 135° for 6 hours. After the reaction the substance was crystallised in a dull yellow crystalline form, m.p. 169°.

Similarly other aldehydes were condensed, yielding 5-arylidene derivatives. Physical properties and analytical data are recorded in Table I.

2-o-Phenetylimino-3-o-phenetyl-5-benzylidene-4-thiazolidone was obtained according to the procedure, mentioned above, by heating in an oil bath at 160° for 3.5 hours. The properties and analytical data of 5-arylidene derivatives obtained by condensation with other aldehydes are mentioned in Table I.

3-o-Anisyl-5-benzylidene-2, 4-thiazolidone.—A mixture of thiazolidone (0.446 g.), benzaldehyde (0.212 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.), and anhydrous sodium acetate (1.0 g.) was heated under reflux for 1.5 hours. On pouring the contents into water and keeping overnight, a yellow precipitate was obtained, which was crystallised from ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 98°. Similarly other aldehydes were condensed, yielding 5-arylidene derivatives. The properties and analytical data are recorded in Table II.

3-o-Phenetyl-5-benzylidene-2, 4-thiazolidone was prepared according to the above method. Similarly other aldehydes were condensed with the thiazolidone. The properties and analytical data are recorded in Table II.

2-o-Phenetylimino-3-o-phenetyl-5-phenylazo-4-thiazolidone was prepared by the method of Bhargava and Goswami (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 763). The thiazolidone was likewise condensed with *p*-toluenediazonium chloride. The properties of these compounds and their analytical data are recorded in Table III. Similarly 5-arylazo derivatives of 3-o-phenetyl-2,4-thiazolidone were prepared as reported in Table III.

2-o-Phenetylimino-3-o-phenetyl-4-thiazolidone Sulphone.—*2-o-Phenetylimino-3-o-phenetyl-4-thiazolidone* (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) and treated slowly with $KMnO_4$ (1 g.), dissolved in water (40 c.c.), at 0°. The precipitate obtained after removing excess of $KMnO_4$ and chilling was washed with ice-cold water, dried, and crystallised from ethanol in a yellow form, m.p. 106°. (Found: S, 8.18. $C_{19}H_{20}O_5N_2S$ requires S, 8.25%).

TABLE I
2-o-Anisylimino-3-o-anisyl-5-arylidene-4-thiazolidones (A) and 2-o-phenetylimino-3-o-phenetyl-5-arylidene-4-thiazolidones (P).

Aldehyde.	A-4-thiazolidones.			P-4-thiazolidones.		
	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.
Benzaldehyde	Yellow	169°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	Pale yellow	121°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂ S
m-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	Grey	145°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	..	..	..
p-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	Yellow	138°	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	Yellow	135°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂ S
o-Chlorobenzaldehyde	..	..	..	Pale yellow	119°	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ ClS
p-Anisaldehyde	Chocolate	161°	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂ S	..	..	..
Cinnamaldehyde	..	..	..	Yellow	120°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂ S
Furfuraldehyde	Grey	196°	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ S	Brown	122°	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S

% Sulphur.
Found. Calc.

TABLE II
3-o-Anisyl-5-arylidene-2, 4-thiazolidones (A') and 3-o-phenetyl-5-arylidene-2, 4-thiazolidones (P').

Aldehyde.	A'-2,4-thiazolidones.			P'-2,4-thiazolidones.		
	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.	Colour.	M.P.	Formula.
Benzaldehyde	Yellow	98°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ NS	Yellow	139°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ NS
m-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	Do	118°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ NS	..	..	..
p-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	Grey	111°	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ NS	..	..	..
o-Chlorobenzaldehyde	..	..	..	Yellow	159°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ NCIS
Cinnamaldehyde	..	..	..	Do	120°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₃ NS
Furfuraldehyde	Brown	75°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ NS	Brown	132°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ NS

% Sulphur.
Found. Calc.

TABLE III
2-o-Phenetylimino-3-o-phenetyl-5-arylazo-4-thiazolidone (P'') and 3-o-phenetyl-5-arylazo-2, 4-thiazolidone (P''').

Diazonium chloride of amines.	P''-2,4-thiazolidone.			P'''-2,4-thiazolidone.		
	*Colour in acetic acid.	M.P.	Formula.	*Colour.	M.P.	Formula.
Aniline	Reddish yellow	116°	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	Brown*	113°	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S
p-Toluidine	Orange	121°	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	..	..	..
p-Phenetidine	..	..	..	Reddish yellow	126°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂ S

% Sulphur.
Found. Calc.

* In acetic acid.

3-*o*-Phenetyl-2, 4-thiazolidione sulphone was prepared and crystallised, as above, in a pale yellow form, m.p. 114°. (Found : S, 11.65. $C_{11}H_{11}O_5NS$ requires S, 11.90).

3-Acetoxymercuri-*o*-anisyl-2, 4-thiazolidione.—To the thiazolidione (1 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.), were added ethanol (15 c.c.) and mercuric acetate (1.5 g.), dissolved in water (15 c.c.) and acidified with acetic acid. After stirring and keeping for 24 hours, a cream-coloured precipitate was obtained, which was filtered, washed with water, dried, and crystallised from ethanol in a yellow form, m.p. 116.5°. (Found : Hg, 41.94. $C_{12}H_{11}O_5NSHg$ requires Hg, 41.66%).

3-Acetoxymercuri-*o*-phenetyl-2, 4-thiazolidione was similarly prepared, as above, in an ash-coloured form, m.p. 102°. (Found : Hg, 40.68. $C_{13}H_{13}O_5NSHg$ requires Hg, 40.44%).

Fungicidal Test

3-Acetoxymercuri-*o*-anisyl-2, 4-thiazolidione was tested for its fungicidal activity on the spores of *Alternaria solani*, parasitic upon *Solanum tuberosum*, Linn, according to the method outlined by Horsefall (*Phytopath.*, 1940, 30, 545) at 20°. The compound is found to be toxic as shown by the inhibition of germination in its presence. It inhibits germination completely up to 66 p.p.m., which is the minimum effective concentration. At 50 and 40 p.p.m., the spore germination is 56% and 84% respectively and below the concentration 33 p.p.m., its activity is nil. The results are tabulated in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Sl. No.	% Conc.	Conc.	Number of spores		% Germination.
			germinated.	ungerminated.	
1.	0.100000 g.	1000.00 p.p.m.	0	150	0
2.	0.010000	100.00	0	150	0
3.	0.006667	66.67	2	148	13
4.	0.005555	55.55	33	117	22
5.	0.005000	50.00	84	66	56
6.	0.004000	40.00	126	24	84
7.	0.003333	33.33	150	0	100

3-Acetoxymercuri-*o*-phenetyl-2, 4-thiazolidione.—The test was carried on thirty days' old spores of *Fusarium nivale* at 20° according to the procedure mentioned above. It has been observed that germination of spores up to 1/35,000 dilution or up to a concentration of 26.58 p.p.m. is completely inhibited.

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